

Data Collection Instruments

This document presents the data collection instruments used in this project. The questionnaire is referred in the paper as (III) for interviews with employees of the physical Social Offices. It was made available online for a period of 9 months, from August 2021 to February 2022.

(III) For interviews with the employees of the physical Social Offices:

The interviews were carried out through a videoconference tool and divided into Informed Consent Form (ICF), demographics, and specific questions, as shown below:

a) ICF for employees: presentation of the ICF and collection of permission through recording of the meeting.

b) Demographic Data Collection (optional fields):

1. Age?
2. Race/ethnicity: IBGE: white; black; brown; yellow; indigenous; Other?
3. Gender Identity: Male; Woman; Non-binary/non-conforming?
4. Are you part of the LGBTQIA+ population? If yes, which group?
5. Do you have a disability? If yes, which one?
6. Are you a foreigner? If yes, from which country?
7. In which physical Social Office do you work?
8. What is your academic background?
9. What is your role in the physical Social Office?
10. Cell phone brand and, if possible, model?

c) Specific questions:

1. What services are most sought after by former inmates at the physical Social Office where you work?
2. Could the reasons that lead former inmates to look for the physical Social Office where you work also be answered virtually through an application?
3. Have you ever used the Virtual Social Office application? If yes, what is your opinion about the Virtual Social Office application?
4. Could you give a grade with comments for the information and functionality available on these services if you have used the application:
 - i. Temporary shelter
 - ii. Food
 - iii. Useful directions and addresses
 - iv. Healthcare facilities
 - v. Documents and benefits
 - vi. Criminal Process status
 - vii. Professional training courses

- viii. Starting over (Work Tips)
- ix. Guardianship of children and teenagers
- x. Treatment for abusive use of alcohol and other drugs
- xi. Stories from other former inmates
- xii. Benefits, financial assistance and other family services
- xiii Free legal assistance
- xiv. Contact the Social Office

5. Have you ever assisted a former inmate who had used the Virtual Social Office application? If yes, did he/she express an opinion about the Virtual Social Office application?
6. Have you already recommended the application to any former inmate or family member? If yes, for how many people?
7. What did you like most about the app?
8. What did you find most difficult about the app?
9. Would you like to add something? Criticisms and suggestions are very welcome.